

MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERVENTION PROGRAMS IN RELATION TO THE INSTITUTIONAL PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN THE FOURTH CONGRESSIONAL DISTRICT OF QUEZON

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the management practices in implementing intervention programs and their relation on institutional performance in public elementary schools within the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon, Philippines. It profiles the schools, evaluates management practices in strategic planning and management, budgeting, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation, and investigates the influence of education level on these practices. The research also analyzes School-Based Management (SBM) practices, explores the relationship between intervention program implementation and school performance, and proposes actionable recommendations. Data were gathered through custom survey questionnaires and analyzed using statistical tools, revealing principals as key decision-makers, a high prevalence of advanced degrees among school heads, and most schools categorized as large. Management practices were found to be effectively implemented, with a significant moderate correlation between intervention programs and institutional performance. Recommendations include continuous monitoring, enhanced reporting, capacity building, budget management, professional development, collaboration, and fostering a culture of continuous improvement. An action plan is proposed, emphasizing goal setting, budget management, stakeholder engagement, and feedback mechanisms, offering insights into improving educational leadership and management strategies.

Keywords: *Management Practices, Intervention Programs, Institutional Performance, Public Elementary Schools, School-Based Management (SBM)*

INTRODUCTION

Achieving quality education requires intentional efforts from institutions. Recognized as a driver of societal progress, education fosters creativity, personal responsibility, and collective growth (UNESCO, 2023).

An intervention program is a structured approach designed to address challenges, improve outcomes, or support goals, often using evidence-based strategies. As Gertler et al. (2016) note, these programs involve planned activities and include monitoring and evaluation to ensure effectiveness.

Effective management ensures proper planning, resource allocation, and stakeholder coordination in intervention programs. It sets clear goals, monitors progress, addresses challenges, and enhances efficiency. Strong management also fosters accountability, transparency, and trust, ensuring sustainability and success.

Gutierrez et al. (2023) emphasized that intervention programs, when aligned with SBM's core principles (leadership, governance, accountability, curriculum improvement, and resource management), can significantly improve school outcomes. Programs that address gaps in documentation and practice can enhance SBM artifacts, which are key requirements for advancing through SBM levels. Tolentino (2023) underscores the crucial role teachers play in successfully implementing reading intervention programs, emphasizing that parental involvement is essential to their effectiveness.

Additionally, intervention programs designed to increase school enrollment rates have been linked to advancements in School-Based Management (SBM) levels by addressing key access and participation metrics, which are crucial to SBM evaluations. The School-Based Management Project in Mexico (PEC) demonstrated that interventions focused on enrollment growth and student retention contributed significantly to improved SBM levels by fostering stronger community collaboration and optimizing resource utilization (World Bank, n.d.).

Furthermore, in the Philippines, SBM assessments use access metrics such as the Net Enrollment Rate (NER) and Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) as key indicators. Programs aimed at improving these metrics can enhance SBM ratings by addressing these specific criteria and encouraging collaboration among stakeholders, ultimately helping to sustain improvements in school operations and overall performance (TeacherPH, n.d.).

However, these metrics can be affected by the learners' academic performance. Maintaining good academic performance can be addressed through intervention programs. Validation in meeting SBM goals is important. Schools at higher SBM level of

practice must demonstrate robust structures, active stakeholder involvement, and consistent learning outcome improvement which can be achieved through effective implementation of intervention programs. As reflected in the SBM Tool implementation, intervention programs and projects are required to receive Level II and Level III SBM Accreditation.

Bucker (2017) highlights that effective educational management relies on structured, outcome-oriented practices. Schools with strong leadership and a focus on continuous improvement achieve higher SBM accreditation levels.

Despite challenges like post-pandemic disruptions and resource constraints, the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon's SBM progress demonstrates that intentional management can bridge performance gaps, foster excellence, and build sustainable systems that empower learners and communities.

This study investigates the management practices of selected public elementary schools in Quezon's fourth congressional district, focusing on the implementation of intervention programs aligned with DepEd Division initiatives. It examines the roles of teachers, SBM coordinators, and school leaders in strategic planning and management, budgeting, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of programs to enhance student performance and institutional outcomes. Additionally, the study explores the link between these practices and schools' institutional performance as reflected in their SBM ratings.

Research Questions

The study aims to determine and identify the management practices in the implementation of the intervention program of the selected public elementary schools in the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon. Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the school profile in terms of the following?
 - 1.1. Designation of School Head
 - 1.2. Educational Attainment of the School Head
 - 1.3. School Size Category
2. What is the respondents' level of management practices regarding the implementation of the intervention programs in terms of the following?
 - 2.1. Strategic Planning and Management
 - 2.2. Budgeting
 - 2.3. Implementation
 - 2.4. Monitoring
 - 2.5. Evaluation
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of management practices of the respondents in the implementation of the intervention programs when grouped into the school profile?

4. What is the institutional performance of the school based on the School-Based Management (SBM) level of practice?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of management practices of intervention programs and school's institutional performance through SBM level of practice?
6. Considering the study's findings, what action plan can the researcher develop to ensure the effective implementation of the intervention programs?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discussed the research design, target demographic and sample, research tools used, methods of data collection, and data analysis techniques.

Research Design

This research study is quantitative and employs a descriptive-correlational design. Descriptive research is a method that involves objectively and systematically observing behavior to describe specific attributes. Correlational research, on the other hand, is a method that describes and predicts how variables are naturally related in the real world, without the researcher attempting to change or assign causation between them. The primary goal of descriptive research is to produce a snapshot of the current state of affairs, whereas correlational research aids in comparing two or more entities or variables (Tullao, 2021).

This study used a descriptive design to assess management practices in implementing the intervention program. The implementation will be evaluated using a 5-point Likert scale to measure the extent of these practices.

On the other hand, the study uses a correlational design to examine the relationship between management practices in implementing the intervention program and institutional performance.

Research Locale

The research study was conducted in Quezon Province, located in the southeastern portion of Metro Manila. It shares borders with the provinces of Aurora to the north, Bulacan, Rizal, Laguna, and Batangas to the west, and Camarines Norte and Camarines Sur to the east. A narrow geographic area connects two more significant regions: the Bicol Peninsula and the main island of Luzon. The Polillo Islands, situated in the Philippine Sea, are also part of the province. Additionally, Quezon Province encompasses the maritime area of the Verde Island Passage, which is home to a significant majority of the world's marine species. Quezon is part of the CALABARZON region on the island of Luzon. Initially, the province was named Kalilayan when it was founded in 1591, but it was changed to Tayabas in the mid-18th century. The province was later renamed Quezon in honor of Manuel L. Quezon, the second president of the

Philippines. Lucena City serves as the province's capital and is the most populated city, characterized as a highly urbanized metropolis.

The Department of Education (DepEd) Quezon is a government agency in the Philippine province of Quezon, focused on ensuring access to high-quality education for all individuals. DepEd Quezon has launched several programs and projects to promote inclusive and equitable education for all residents of the province, operating under fundamental educational principles.

Currently, the Department of Education Division of Quezon is recognized as the largest school division in the Philippines among the 19 divisions. This division is divided into four identifiable congressional districts: the first, second, third, and fourth.

In this study, the researcher focuses on selected public elementary schools in the municipalities of Alabat Island, Gumaca, Lopez, and Guinayangan, all located within the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon. This locale was chosen to thoroughly investigate whether a significant relationship exists between the level of management practices in implementing intervention programs and the institutional performance of these schools.

Population and Sampling

The researcher employed a clustering sampling technique to analyze school districts, using purposive sampling based on school size categories and supported by documents from Quezon Division Memorandum No. 216, s. 2022. This memorandum provided a list of schools subject to onsite validation, specifically those with an advanced level of school-based management practice (SBM-LoP) according to self-assessment results referenced in Division Memorandum No. 28, s. 2022, titled "Report on SBM Level of Practice for S.Y. 2020-2021." The researcher selected three respondents from each municipality—ideally one large, medium, and small school. This resulted in a total population of 11 elementary school heads and 151 teachers from the selected schools.

Bhandari (2022) highlighted the key difference between a population and a sample in his study. The population refers to the entire group about which conclusions are sought, while the sample is a specific subset of that population from which data is collected. It is important to note that the sample size is always smaller than the total population. This distinction highlights the necessity of working with samples, as practical, financial, and time constraints often make it challenging—if not impossible—to gather data from the entire population. Samples serve as representative subsets, allowing researchers to draw generalizations about the broader population.

Table 1*Respondents of the Study in Fourth Congressional District of Quezon*

Cluster Municipality	District	School Size	School	Population		Sample	
				School Head	Teacher	School Head	Teacher
Alabat, Perez, Quezon	Alabat	Large	A	1	49	1	25
		Medium	B	1	14	1	9
		Small	C	1	6	1	4
Atimonan, Plaridel, Gumaca	Gumaca	Large	D	1	49	1	27
		Medium	E	1	23	1	16
		Small	F	1	8	1	6
Lopez, Calauag	Lopez	Large	G	1	42	1	22
		Medium	H	1	14	1	10
		Small	I	1	2	1	2
Tagkawayan, Guinayangan	Guinayangan	Large	J	1	45	1	25
		Small	K	1	6	1	5
Total				11	258	11	151

As presented in the above table, there is no medium school presented in Guinayangan District. The researcher conducts the study in the medium school and gets the research instrument to validate their management practices in the implementation of intervention programs, but the complete data on SBM is not available due to some reasons. The coordinator of SBM does not intentionally misplace the record of the School-Based Management (SBM) result as needed for the complete findings for correlation in the research study. That's why the researcher decided to not include their responses in management practices in the implementation of intervention programs.

Research Instrument

The research questionnaire was utilized as the primary instrument to assess the management practices in implementing intervention programs and the performance of schools based on their level of School-Based Management (SBM) practices. It comprised three main parts:

Part I: This section gathered demographic information about the respondents, including school head designation, educational attainment, and school size category.

Part II: The questionnaire assessed the respondents' practice in implementing management related to strategic planning and management, budgeting, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation.

Part III: This section focused on evaluating institutional performance based on the level of school-based management (SBM) practices among the respondents.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, the researcher took several steps. First, they obtained permission from three experts—a public school district supervisor and two education program supervisors—to review the instrument. Second, a

pre-test was conducted with thirty (30) respondents who were not part of the sample, and reliability was computed using Cronbach's alpha.

The questionnaire employed a 5-point Likert scale, where participants indicated their degree of agreement or disagreement with a series of statements. Additionally, the interpretation of the level of management practices in implementing intervention programs utilized a scale with corresponding verbal interpretations based on the range of values.

Likert Scale to Measure the Management Practices in the Implementation of Intervention Programs in Selected Public Elementary School in the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon

Scale	Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
5	4.20-5.00	Practiced to the Greatest Extent	Management practices have been fully implemented and played a critical role in the overwhelming success of the intervention program.
4	3.40-4.19	Practiced to the Great Extent	Management practices have been extensively implemented and have a substantial positive impact on the intervention program.
3	2.60-3.39	Practiced to the Moderate Extent	Management practices have been implemented to a moderate extent and have contributed somewhat to the success of the school.
2	1.80-2.59	Practiced to the Less Extent	Management practices have been implemented, but the impact on the intervention program is minimal.
1	1.00-1.79	Did Not Practice at All	Management practices have been not implemented at all.

Data Gathering Procedures

After validating the research instrument, written permissions were obtained from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) and the District Supervisor (DS) of each selected public elementary school in the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon. Additionally, consent was obtained from the respondents in the target population to complete the enhanced self-made survey questionnaires.

Purposive sampling was used to select sampling units subjectively, allowing for a focused evaluation of management practices in implementing intervention programs and assessing the institutional performance of the schools.

Upon approval, the questionnaires were distributed using online Google Forms and printed survey forms. In the online survey, the researcher explained the study's objectives and clarified any relevant terms to ensure that respondents could answer the questions honestly and to the best of their ability. Once respondents completed either the online Google Form survey or the printed questionnaire, the results were automatically collected for checking, tallying, interpretation, and analysis.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data collected in this study underwent analysis using various statistical tools:

For Statement of the Problem 1, the researcher used descriptive statistics, including frequency distribution and percentages, to summarize the number of school heads in each designation category (Principal, Head Teacher, and Teacher-in-Charge), to present the different levels of educational attainment (Bachelor's, Master's, Doctorate), and to classify schools into size categories (small, medium, and large) based on teacher population and other criteria.

For Statement of the Problem 2, to determine the respondents' level of management practices regarding the implementation of intervention programs, the researcher used descriptive statistics to identify the level of practice based on the provided scale. The mean, median, and standard deviation were computed to summarize the central tendency and variability for each aspect (strategic planning and management, budgeting, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation).

For Statement of the Problem 3, to examine the difference in the level of management practices of the respondents in implementing the intervention programs when grouped by school profile, the researcher employed inferential statistics using ANOVA to compare groups of respondents based on their designation, educational attainment, and school size categories.

To address Statement of the Problem 4, the researcher analyzed the institutional performance of the school respondents based on their School-Based Management (SBM) level of practice using descriptive statistics. Frequency distribution, percentages, and mean scores were used to summarize the SBM level of practice.

For Statement of the Problem 5, to determine the significant relationship between the level of management practices in intervention programs and institutional performance through SBM level of practice, the researcher applied Correlation Analysis using Pearson's correlation.

To interpret the results of Pearson's Product Moment of Correlation, the study relied on a predetermined continuum:

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1	1.00-1.79	Did Not Practice at All	Management practices have been not implemented at all.

Size of Correlation	Interpretation
±1.00	Perfectly positive/ negative correlation
±0.90 – 0.99	Very high positive/ negative correlation
±0.70 – 0.89	High positive/ negative correlation
±0.50 – 0.69	Moderately positive/ negative correlation
±0.30 – 0.49	Low positive/ negative correlation
±0.01 – 0.29	Negligible correlation
0.00	No correlation at all

RESULTS

Part I. Profile of the School

This study analyzed participants' profiles to explore how various factors influence management practices in implementing intervention programs and their varying effects on institutional performance. A total of 162 respondents which include 11 school head and 151 teachers from selected public elementary schools in Quezon's Fourth Congressional District participated in this research.

Table 2

Level of Management Practices of the Respondents in the Implementation of Intervention Programs in Terms of Strategic Planning and Management

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Designation of School Head		
Teacher-in-Charge	1	9.09
Head Teacher	3	27.27
Principal	7	63.64
<hr/>		
Total	11	100.00
Educational Attainment of the School Head		
Bachelor's degree Holder	0	0.0
With Earned Units in Masters	2	18.18
Master's degree Holder	4	36.36
With Earned Units in Doctorate	3	27.27
Doctoral Degree Holder	2	18.18
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Total	11	100.00
School Category		
Small	4	36.36%
Medium	3	27.27
Large	4	36.36
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Total	11	100.00

Table 2 shows that the distribution of respondents across different categories provides valuable insights into the educational landscape within the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon. Principals emerge as the predominant group, comprising 63.64% of the respondents, underscoring their central role in school management and instructional leadership. This aligns with the regulatory framework outlined in Republic Act No. 9155, which mandates that every public elementary and secondary school must have a designated school head. The pivotal role of Principals is further emphasized by their responsibilities in developing and implementing school policies and intervention programs initiatives.

In support of the result, according to Section 6.1, Rule VI, of the Implementing Rules and Regulations of Republic Act No. 9155, the control over the management; Management and instruction of a school rests with the school principal. This underscores the multifaceted nature of their leadership, encompassing educational, people, and strategic dimensions. Principals are expected to demonstrate educational leadership by developing a shared school vision and mission, designing curriculum-related initiatives, and fostering a conducive learning environment. Their role also includes leading people, collaborating with stakeholders, and positively influencing others to achieve

organizational goals. Strategic leadership is also crucial, as Principals must manage educational institutions, address complex issues, and optimize resource utilization.

These observations underscore the substantial responsibilities of school administrators, who play a crucial role in driving educational reforms and intervention programs. Understanding the distribution of respondents' designations is essential for interpreting their roles and contributions within the educational framework of the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon. This context provides a more precise basis for analyzing their influence and participation in the district's educational landscape.

In terms of educational attainment, the data show that 36.36% of respondents have completed a master's degree, while an additional 18.18% have earned credits toward a master's degree. Additionally, 18.18% hold doctoral degrees, and the same percentage (18.18%) have earned credits in a doctoral program. Notably, none of the respondents possess barely a bachelor's degree.

This distribution underscores the high level of educational attainment among school administrators in the district, with a substantial portion having pursued advanced degrees. In connection to this, according to Pato (2023), such educational credentials equip school administrators with specialized knowledge and expertise in educational theories, pedagogy, leadership techniques, and policy frameworks. Their deep understanding enables them to engage effectively in strategic planning and decision-making. The findings corroborate also with previous research by Aguinis (2019), Antley (2020), and Suyitno (2020), which highlight the positive impact of professional growth and development on academic and school performance. Thus, the prevalence of advanced degrees among school heads in the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon suggests a commitment to ongoing learning and professional development within the educational leadership landscape.

The data shows that most respondents at 36.36% are affiliated with large schools. small-sized schools account for 36.36%, followed by medium schools at 27.27%. This breakdown provides valuable insights into the composition of school heads, their educational qualifications, and the types of schools they oversee.

The influence of school size on learning outcomes is a topic of ongoing debate, as evidenced by research findings. In connection to this result, studies in the USA suggest that smaller schools may enhance student outcomes by fostering community among students, teachers, and parents (Barrett et al., 2019). Conversely, research in India indicates that small schools may perform poorly due to resource constraints and a lack of specialized teachers (Rolleston & Moore, 2018).

Interestingly, data from Senegal suggest that attendance at large schools may negatively impact students' performance by the fourth grade. In contrast, school size does not affect performance in the early grades (Koussihouede, 2020). This disparity could be attributed to the differing influences of family environment on younger learners, who may not yet be significantly impacted by school size.

Research by Barrett et al. (2019) highlights several disadvantages of large schools, such as increased transportation costs, higher administrative overhead, lower teacher satisfaction, elevated absenteeism, and decreased graduation rates. These findings underscore the complexity of the relationship between school size and educational outcomes, suggesting that various contextual factors must be considered when interpreting the impact of school size on student performance.

Part II. Management Practices in the Implementation of Intervention Programs

Table 3

*Level of Management Practices of the Respondents in the Implementation of Intervention Programs in Terms of **Strategic Planning and Management***

Indicators	Frequency	Total Mean	SD	VI
1. Collaborate with the school head and program coordinators to design a comprehensive intervention program plan and set clear objectives.		4.42	0.628	PGtE
2. Develop a well-structured schedule or timetable for the intervention program.		4.31	0.595	PGtE
3. Establish effective and transparent communication channels with parents and various community stakeholders to facilitate the seamless implementation of intervention programs.		4.33	0.658	PGtE
4. Ensure that the intervention program is closely aligned with the overarching goals of the school.		4.46	0.622	PGtE
5. Clearly articulate how the program supports the school's broader mission and vision		4.42	0.597	PGtE
6. Optimize the allocation of available resources - both material and human - to bolster the intervention program.		4.23	0.701	PGtE
7. Demonstrate responsible spending and maintain transparent budget practices.		4.27	0.746	PGtE
8. Foster active participation from teachers, parents, students, and community members in shaping the intervention program's plans and decision-making processes.		4.37	0.639	PGtE
9. Set up key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure the effectiveness and progress of the school's initiatives.		4.33	0.658	PGtE
10. Regularly evaluate and analyze data to identify progress and address setbacks.		4.29	0.627	PGtE
11. Possess the flexibility to adapt the intervention program in response to evolving needs, challenges, and feedback.		4.34	0.622	PGtE
12. Embrace a philosophy of continuous improvement as the guiding principle.		4.31	0.671	PGtE
13. Ensure that school administrators are equipped with the skills and efficiency to manage the program effectively.		4.32	0.666	PGtE
14. Uphold accountability and transparency in the decision-making process.		4.36	0.656	PGtE
15. Provide opportunities for teacher development and training related to the intervention program.		4.38	0.651	PGtE
16. Assess the impact of teachers on instructional methods and classroom practices.		4.33	0.667	PGtE
17. Gauge the level of parental and local community stakeholder engagement and support for intervention programs.		4.25	0.669	PGtE
18. Evaluate the evidences of partnership of parents and the local community with Government Organizations (GOs) and Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) when it comes to outsourcing of funds for specific intervention programs.		4.23	0.718	PGtE
19. Conduct regular evaluations to gauge the effectiveness and impact of intervention programs on institutional performance.		4.24	0.676	PGtE
20. Monitor improvements in students' academic performance, including test results, graduation rates, and attendance.		4.42	0.618	PGtE
21. Track changes in students' attitudes, involvement, and overall well-being.		4.43	0.599	PGtE

22. Implement strategies and plans to ensure the sustainability of the intervention program.	4.34	0.632	PGtE
Composite Mean	4.34	0.651	PGtE

Legend:

Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Practiced to the Greatest Extent (PGtE)
3.40 – 4.19	Practiced to the Great Extent (PGE)
2.60 – 3.39	Practiced to the Moderate Extent (PME)
1.80 – 2.59	Practiced to the Less Extent (PLE)
1.00 – 1.79	Did Not Practice at All (DNP)

Table 3 presents an evaluation of respondents' management practices in implementing intervention programs focusing on strategic planning and management. Each indicator is rated on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents minimal practice and 5 represents extensive practice.

Overall, the respondents demonstrate a high level of management practices in strategic planning and the implementation of intervention programs, with a composite mean score (M) of 4.34 (SD = 0.651) indicating that these practices are predominantly implemented to a “Practiced to the Greatest Extent” (PGtE).

The key findings highlight several critical areas in the management of intervention programs. A strong collaboration with school heads, teachers and program coordinators to design comprehensive intervention plans and set clear objectives obtained a mean (M) of 4.42 with a standard deviation (SD) of 0.628 described as "Practiced to a Greatest Extent" (PGtE). Establishing effective and transparent communication channels with parents and various community stakeholders to facilitate the seamless implementation of intervention programs obtained a mean score (M) of 4.33 (SD = 0.658) described as "Practiced to a Great Extent" (PGtE). The responses show that the majority rated this as "5" (n = 69) or "4" (n = 78), reflecting strong agreement with this indicator. While efforts to optimize resource allocation is slightly less practiced, obtaining a mean of 4.23 (SD = 0.701). Regular evaluation and analyzing data to identify progress and address setbacks of intervention programs is a standard practice, as indicated by a mean score of 4.29 (SD = 0.627) described as “Practiced to the Greatest Extent”. There is a significant emphasis on accountability and transparency in decision-making processes as described in the obtained mean score (M) of 4.36 (SD = 0.656) described as “Practiced to the Greatest Extent” (PGtE). Additionally, respondents embrace a philosophy of continuous improvement in managing these programs, reflected in a mean score (M) of 4.31 (SD = 0.671) described as “Practiced to the Greatest Extent” (PGtE).

The analysis suggests a commendable adoption of strategic management practices. Within intervention program management, as evidenced by most indicators falling within the "Practiced to the Greatest Extent" (PGtE) category. This indicates a proactive stance toward improving educational outcomes through well-structured and efficiently managed intervention programs. Efficient strategic planning, as highlighted by Sallis (2012), involves a systematic Approach encompassing decision-making, management, and quality improvement processes. Bryson and George (2020) further underscore the pivotal role of strategic planning and management in realizing organizational goals and generating public value. However, it is crucial to recognize that

the efficacy of strategic planning techniques can be influenced by contextual factors, necessitating adaptive and thoughtful application.

In support to the above statement within educational contexts, strategic planning serves as a guiding force for institutions. They are aiming at quality enhancement and coherent progress, echoing Sallis's (2012) insights. Meyers and VanGronigen (2019) emphasize the significance of aligning strategic plans with the school's mission and executing them effectively to foster improvement. Despite these efforts, persistent challenges such as knowledge gaps among stakeholders and the imperative for evidence-based planning and evaluation processes, as noted by Acton (2021) and Schildkamp (2019), remain areas of concern. These challenges underscore the ongoing need for iterative refinement, and the enhancement of strategic planning practices within educational settings.

Table 4
Level of Management Practices of the Respondents in the Implementation of Intervention Programs in Terms of Budgeting

Indicators	Frequency	Total		
		Mean	SD	VI
1. Optimize the allocation of the school budget dedicated to intervention programs.		4.04	0.751	PGE
2. Provide a clearly defined and easily accessible budget document for intervention programs.		4.00	0.796	PGE
3. Ensure consistent alignment of budget allocation with the goals of the intervention programs.		4.01	0.808	PGE
4. Conduct regular and effective monitoring of the budget to ensure that it meets program needs.		3.98	0.830	PGE
5. Establish mechanisms to enforce accountability among those overseeing budget utilization.		3.96	0.863	PGE
6. Demonstrate the ability to adapt the budget to changing program requirements and priorities.		3.98	0.860	PGE
7. Diversify resources effectively to support intervention programs.		4.06	0.766	PGE
8. Evaluate the efficiency of resource utilization in achieving program goals.		4.06	0.798	PGE
9. Encourage the participation of relevant stakeholders in the budget decision-making process.		4.11	0.804	PGE
10. Align the budget with the strategic goals of the school.		4.06	0.809	PGE
11. Sustain intervention programs within budget constraints.		4.03	0.822	PGE
12. Include a contingency plan in the budget for unforeseen financial challenges.		3.99	0.808	PGE
13. Ensure accessibility of resources for all students and staff involved in intervention programs.		4.03	0.815	PGE
14. Provide regular reports on budget status and its impact on program outcomes.		4.02	0.874	PGE
15. Assess the cost-effectiveness of intervention programs.		4.01	0.834	PGE
16. Evaluate the school's reliance on external grant funding and its impact on program stability.		4.06	0.821	PGE
17. Offer budget management training to staff involved in the programs.		4.00	0.871	PGE
18. Equitably distribute resources among the different schools in the district.		4.01	0.756	PGE
19. Manage and reinvest surplus budget funds.		3.94	0.824	PGE
20. Implement a systematic evaluation of the budgeting process for ongoing improvement.		3.99	0.808	PGE
Composite Mean		4.02	0.816	PGE

Legend:

Mean Range **Verbal Interpretation**
4.20 – 5.00 Practiced to the Greatest Extent (PGtE)

3.40 – 4.19	<i>Practiced to the Great Extent (PGE)</i>
2.60 – 3.39	<i>Practiced to the Moderate Extent (PME)</i>
1.80 – 2.59	<i>Practiced to the Less Extent (PLE)</i>
1.00 – 1.79	<i>Did Not Practice at All (DNP)</i>

Table 4 presents data on the level of management practices related to budgeting in the implementation of intervention programs, as perceived by the respondents. Overall, these Management practices are rated relatively high, with a composite mean (M) of 4.02 (SD = 0.816) described as “Practiced to the Great Extent (PGE)”. Most indicators obtained mean Ratings above (M) 4.06 (SD = 0.766), suggesting widespread agreement that these practices are well-implemented. Specifically, Indicator 7 focuses on diversifying resources effectively to support intervention programs, while Indicator 8 evaluates the efficiency of resource utilization in achieving program goals. Indicator 9 involves setting up key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure the effectiveness and progress of the school's initiatives, Indicator 10 aligns the budget with the school's strategic goals, and Indicator 16 evaluates the school's reliance on external grant funding and its impact on program stability. These indicators have exceptionally high mean ratings, indicating strong agreement on the effectiveness of practices related to stakeholder participation, alignment with strategic goals, and assessment of grant funding impact.

While most indicators have relatively low standard deviations, indicating consensus among respondents, indicators 14 provide regular reports on budget status and its impact on program outcomes. And 17 offer budget management training to staff involved in the programs show higher standard deviations, but in these indicators, there are some responses falling into the categories of 'practiced to a lesser extent' and 'not practiced at all,' similar to other indicators.

The findings highlight that all indicators fall within the categories of "Practiced to a Moderate Extent" (PME), underscoring the effectiveness of the budgeting efforts implemented in the educational setting. It aligns with the emphasis on budgeting by Acido and Kilongkilong (2022), who assert that budgeting serves as a cornerstone of sound financial management, ensuring effective resource allocation and expenditure oversight. The findings also reflect Usman's (2016) perspective, which underscores the critical role of planning and resource control in achieving educational goals.

Moreover, the cautionary insights of Bua and Adzongo (2014) resonate with the need to guard against financial mismanagement, which can negatively impact institutional outcomes.

Additionally, Tria (2020) emphasizes the importance of long-term goal setting and comprehensive assessments, which align with the study's findings that effective budgeting practices support meaningful and sustained educational improvements.

Table 5**Level of Management Practices of the Respondents in the Implementation of Intervention Programs in Terms of *Implementation***

Indicators	Frequency	Total		
		Mean	SD	VI
1. Meet the set timelines for program implementation.		4.14	0.787	PGE
2. Efficiently utilize the available resources during implementation.		4.18	0.779	PGE
3. Provide adequate training for staff involved in program implementation.		4.13	0.757	PGE
4. Involve teachers, parents, and community members in the implementation process.		4.31	0.664	PGtE
5. Define a well-structured plan for communicating program updates and progress.		4.35	0.645	PGtE
6. Continuously monitor to ensure the program meets established quality standards.		4.21	0.691	PGtE
7. Regularly collect feedback from stakeholders on the program's implementation.		4.12	0.737	PGE
8. Adjust based on real-time feedback and changing circumstances.		4.17	0.710	PGE
9. Ensure that the program aligns with the school's strategic goals.		4.24	0.685	PGtE
10. Establish a system for the ongoing evaluation of the program's effectiveness.		4.17	0.710	PGE
11. Define roles and responsibilities for everyone involved in the implementation.		4.27	0.723	PGtE
12. Gauge the level of support and engagement of the local community.		4.16	0.747	PGE
13. Measure the extent to which parents actively participate in the program.		4.14	0.730	PGE
14. Document the program's progress and outcomes appropriately.		4.31	0.718	PGtE
15. Consistently collect and analyze data related to the program.		4.22	0.675	PGtE
16. Address and resolve issues that arise during implementation.		4.23	0.671	PGtE
17. Involve students in the program to an appropriate degree.		4.30	0.713	PGtE
18. Allocate resources to specific program components as planned.		4.19	0.752	PGtE
19. Have a plan in place to sustain the program beyond its initial implementation phase.		4.24	0.712	PGtE
20. Demonstrate commitment to continuously improving the program's implementation process.		4.22	0.720	PGtE
21. Analyze changes in test scores, grades, and graduation rates to gauge how well students are performing academically.		4.28	0.689	PGtE
22. Assess the degree to which discipline, attendance, and behavior of the kids have improved.		4.28	0.673	PGtE
Composite Mean		4.22	0.713	PGtE

Legend:

Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Practiced to the Greatest Extent (PGtE)
3.40 – 4.19	Practiced to the Great Extent (PGE)
2.60 – 3.39	Practiced to the Moderate Extent (PME)
1.80 – 2.59	Practiced to the Less Extent (PLE)
1.00 – 1.79	Did Not Practice at All (DNP)

Table 5 illustrates the level of management practices related to the implementation of intervention programs, specifically focusing on their execution. The high implementation scores suggest that organizations are generally effective in executing these processes, with most indicators receiving mean scores above 4.00 and a composite mean (M) of 4.22 (SD = 0.713) described as “Practiced to the Greatest Extent” (PGtE).

This is consistent with the findings of Klug et al. (2018), Schultes et al. (2019), Lewis & Dorsey (2020), Sørлие et al. (2021), and Feely et al. (2018), all of whom highlight the critical importance of quality implementation for the success of intervention programs. These studies emphasize that successful interventions rely on strong organizational practices, including clear communication, continuous monitoring, and ongoing adaptation to stakeholder needs—all of which are reflected in the high ratings for indicators such as involving teachers, parents, and community members (Indicator 4), defining clear roles and responsibilities (Indicator 11), and ensuring continuous monitoring and feedback (Indicators 6 and 7).

Furthermore, the emphasis in the literature on the alignment of interventions with strategic goals (Klug et al., 2018; Lewis & Dorsey, 2020) is mirrored in the high ratings for indicators like ensuring program alignment with strategic goals (Indicator 9) and documenting progress and outcomes (Indicator 14). These practices demonstrate the organizations' commitment to aligning interventions with broader organizational objectives, ensuring accountability, and fostering long-term success.

The importance of stakeholder engagement and program sustainability, as stressed by Feely et al. (2018) and Sørлие et al. (2021), is also evident in the high ratings for Indicators 19 and 20, which emphasize the long-term engagement and continuous improvement of the programs. These efforts are crucial for sustaining the impact of intervention programs beyond their initial phases.

Lastly, the focus on assessing academic performance and behavioral outcomes, as underscored by Schultes et al. (2019) and Sørлие (2021), aligns with the high ratings for Indicators 21 and 22. These indicators emphasize the organizations' dedication to evaluating and improving the effectiveness of their interventions—an essential component of ensuring the success of any intervention program. This aligns with the idea proposed by Klug et al. (2018), that measuring implementation outcomes through competent delivery and organizational factors is vital for ensuring the quality and effectiveness of interventions.

The findings from this study resonate with the broader literature on quality implementation, reinforcing that successful interventions require a comprehensive approach, including effective planning, stakeholder involvement, continuous monitoring, alignment with strategic goals, and thorough evaluation of outcomes. By adhering to these best practices, as demonstrated in this study, organizations can achieve sustained and meaningful improvements in intervention program effectiveness.

Table 6

Level of Management Practices of the Respondents in the Implementation of Intervention Programs in Terms of Monitoring

Indicators	Frequency	Total		
		Mean	SD	VI
1. Regularly verify the alignment of intervention program activities with institutional objectives.		4.30	0.619	PGIE
2. Evaluate the effectiveness of the monitoring process in ensuring efficient resource utilization for intervention programs.		4.27	0.621	PGIE

3. Track the progress of intervention program activities to ensure the timely attainment of set targets and goals.	4.31	0.623	PGtE
4. Monitor the level of stakeholder engagement and participation in the evaluation process of intervention programs.	4.31	0.691	PGtE
5. Assess the quality of data collection methods employed to monitor the effectiveness of intervention programs.	4.28	0.673	PGtE
6. Monitor changes in pupils' scores on standardized tests or other measures of their academic achievement before and after intervention program implementation.	4.33	0.630	PGtE
7. Track student attendance rates to make sure that interventions are having a beneficial effect on students' attendance at school.	4.32	0.656	PGtE
8. Oversee the implementation of action plans derived from the monitoring process to address identified issues or challenges.	4.28	0.662	PGtE
9. Monitor the level of student engagement and participation in various components of the intervention programs.	4.30	0.670	PGtE
10. Track the integration of feedback from teachers, students, and community members to enhance the effectiveness of the intervention programs.	4.24	0.694	PGtE
11. Evaluate how monitoring contributes to the continuous professional development of teachers involved in intervention programs.	4.27	0.721	PGtE
12. Monitor the maintenance and upkeep of school to support the successful implementation of intervention programs.	4.25	0.690	PGtE
13. Assess the regularity and effectiveness of communication channels between the school administration and stakeholders regarding the progress of intervention programs.	4.30	0.668	PGtE
14. Evaluate the effectiveness of monitoring in identifying and rectifying any gaps or deficiencies in the implementation of intervention programs.	4.29	0.693	PGtE
15. Track the regular assessment of teaching methodologies and their impact on student learning outcomes within the intervention programs.	4.27	0.660	PGtE
16. Monitor the level of satisfaction and engagement of students in the learning activities provided by the intervention programs.	4.26	0.646	PGtE
17. Evaluate the effectiveness of monitoring to ensure compliance of intervention programs with educational standards and guidelines.	4.23	0.683	PGtE
18. Track the level of community involvement and support in monitoring and improving the intervention programs.	4.23	0.710	PGtE
19. Monitor the frequency and quality of monitoring reports provided to relevant educational authorities and stakeholders.	4.23	0.701	PGtE
20. Assess how monitoring fosters a culture of continuous improvement and innovation in the implementation of intervention programs.	4.25	0.660	PGtE
21. Track the implementation of recommendations derived from the monitoring process to enhance the overall effectiveness of intervention programs.	4.22	0.647	PGtE
22. Evaluate the impact of the monitoring process on the overall institutional performance and the success of the intervention programs in public elementary schools within the Quezon Fourth Congressional District.	4.20	0.688	PGtE
Composite Mean	4.27	0.668	PGtE

Legend:

Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Practiced to the Greatest Extent (PGtE)
3.40 – 4.19	Practiced to the Great Extent (PGE)
2.60 – 3.39	Practiced to the Moderate Extent (PME)
1.80 – 2.59	Practiced to the Less Extent (PLE)
1.00 – 1.79	Did Not Practice at All (DNP)

Table 6 provides insights into the level of management practices regarding the monitoring of intervention programs. The data suggests that management practices related to the monitoring of intervention programs are perceived to be implemented described as “Practiced to the Greatest Extent” (PGtE) by the respondents, with an overall composite mean (M) of 4.27 (SD = 0.668). This indicates a strong commitment to effective monitoring within the organizations surveyed.

This finding resonates strongly with the work of Fixsen et al. (2021), who emphasize that monitoring is crucial at all stages of a project—from inception through implementation and completion. The high ratings for indicators such as “regularly verifying alignment with institutional objectives” (M = 4.30, SD = 0.619) described as “Practiced to the Greatest Extent” (PGtE) and “tracking progress toward set targets” underscore the proactive monitoring practices reported in the study, which ensure that intervention programs stay on track and aligned with organizational goals, just as Fixsen et al. (2021) highlight the importance of monitoring for ensuring that activities proceed according to plan.

According to Anderson (2013, as cited in Adow et al., 2020), the importance of continuous monitoring and evaluation is highlighted through the regular review of accounting records and reporting procedures to oversee financial allocations in intervention programs. This perspective aligns with findings that emphasize the significance of monitoring stakeholder engagement and incorporating feedback from teachers, students, and community members (M = 4.24, SD = 0.694) described as “Practice to the Greatest Extent” (PGtE). These practices underscore the necessity of implementing robust monitoring mechanisms to track both financial and operational progress, ensuring transparency and efficiency throughout the intervention's implementation.

Additionally, Ntsele (2014, as cited in Adow et al., 2020) highlights the critical role of monitoring procurement plans and comparing actual expenditures to commitments to ensure a clear understanding of a project's financial status. This perspective is reflected in this study's focus on maintaining communication with stakeholders and providing regular monitoring reports to relevant authorities. Such practices align with Ntsele's emphasis on transparency and detailed financial reporting, fostering stakeholder engagement and informed decision-making.

Moreover, the research findings on evaluating the impact of monitoring on institutional performance and the success of intervention programs resonate with Fixsen et al. (2021)'s assertion that monitoring not only tracks progress but also informs the refinement of processes to improve overall outcomes. This study's strong emphasis on using monitoring data for continuous improvement and supporting staff professional development reflects this ongoing commitment to refining interventions based on real-time feedback, as suggested by Fixsen et al. (2021).

Table 7*Level of Management Practices of the Respondents in the Implementation of Intervention Programs in Terms of **Evaluation***

Indicators	Frequency	Total Mean	SD	VI
1. Evaluate the contribution of intervention programs towards achieving the overall goals and objectives.		4.33	0.640	PGtE
2. Evaluate the effectiveness of the evaluation process in gauging the impact of management practices on the success of intervention programs.		4.27	0.685	PGtE
3. Analyze the alignment of evaluation criteria with the specific outcomes and targets of the intervention programs.		4.30	0.660	PGtE
4. Assess stakeholder involvement and satisfaction levels in the evaluation process of the intervention programs.		4.27	0.714	PGtE
5. Ensure the quality and reliability of data collected during the evaluation of intervention programs.		4.29	0.711	PGtE
6. Review the implementation of improvement measures based on the findings of the program evaluation.		4.29	0.647	PGtE
7. Evaluate the learning outcomes and academic performance of students influenced by the intervention programs.		4.28	0.758	PGtE
8. Gauge the extent to which the evaluation process incorporates feedback from teachers, students, and community members for program.		4.27	0.714	PGtE
9. Monitor the effectiveness of professional development initiatives for teachers based on the evaluation of their performance within the intervention programs.		4.29	0.728	PGtE
10. Evaluate the level of transparency and communication in disseminating evaluation results to stakeholders and relevant authorities.		4.27	0.754	PGtE
11. Evaluate the effectiveness of the evaluation process in identifying strengths and weaknesses in the implementation of intervention programs.		4.30	0.695	PGtE
12. Assess the satisfaction levels of students and teachers with the content and delivery of the intervention programs.		4.30	0.686	PGtE
13. Verify the adherence of the intervention programs to educational standards and guidelines during the evaluation process.		4.31	0.690	PGtE
14. Monitor the extent of community engagement and support in the evaluation and improvement of intervention programs.		4.25	0.699	PGtE
15. Evaluate the timeliness and accuracy of evaluation reports provided to stakeholders and educational authorities.		4.28	0.682	PGtE
16. Assess the impact of the evaluation process on fostering a culture of continuous improvement and innovation within intervention programs.		4.22	0.762	PGtE
17. Track the implementation of recommendations derived from the evaluation process to enhance the overall effectiveness of intervention programs.		4.28	0.682	PGtE
18. Evaluate the overall institutional performance based on the results and findings of the evaluation of intervention programs.		4.27	0.723	PGtE
19. Assess the extent to which intervention programs have improved student performance,		4.27	0.696	PGtE

as measured by grades, graduation rates, and scores on standardized tests.			
20. Evaluate how the behavior of the students has changed, taking into account attendance, involvement in class, and disciplinary occurrences.	4.24	0.685	PGtE
21. Assess the degree to which teachers work together and exchange best practices when putting intervention strategies into practice.	4.29	0.711	PGtE
22. Assess the sustainability and scalability of intervention programs based on the outcomes of the evaluation process in public elementary schools within the Quezon Fourth Congressional District.	4.27	0.712	PGtE
Composite Mean	4.28	0.702	PGtE

Legend:

Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Practiced to the Greatest Extent (PGtE)
3.40 – 4.19	Practiced to the Great Extent (PGE)
2.60 – 3.39	Practiced to the Moderate Extent (PME)
1.80 – 2.59	Practiced to the Less Extent (PLE)
1.00 – 1.79	Did Not Practice at All (DNP)

Table 7 provides valuable insights into the management practices related to the evaluation of intervention programs. The data reveals high mean scores (M) ranging from 4.22 to 4.33, indicating that respondents perceive these practices described as “Practiced to the Greatest Extent” (PGtE). The composite mean (M) of 4.28 (SD = 0.702) reinforces this conclusion, highlighting the overall level of implementation across all evaluation-related indicators as described “Practiced to the Greatest Extent” (PGtE). The finding is parallel with the study of Ntsele (2014), as referenced by Adow et al. (2020), who found that evaluations are a critical tool for securing government support, attracting funding, and promoting the success of interventions. The findings in this study, particularly the emphasis on evaluating the effectiveness of programs, show a clear commitment to these same objectives, as evaluations inform key stakeholders and help demonstrate the value of the programs.

The low standard deviation (SD) values (ranging from 0.640 to 0.762) suggest a high level of agreement among respondents regarding the evaluation practices being implemented. This consistency of opinion highlights the importance placed on rigorous evaluation methods within the organizations. This aligns with Ntsele’s (2014) view, as cited by Adow et al. (2020), that rigorous monitoring and evaluation processes are essential for the credibility of evaluation findings. The high consensus in the study further strengthens the claim that organizations are committed to using precise and reliable indicators for program evaluation.

Furthermore, the importance of selecting appropriate indicators for accurate performance evaluation is underscored by your findings. Indicators related to program evaluation, which received high mean scores, reflect a commitment to precise assessment and ensuring that the intervention programs are having their intended impact. As Ntsele (2014) mentions, pre-selecting relevant indicators is a crucial step in conducting an accurate evaluation that not only measures program outputs but also assesses the

outcomes effectively. This is reflected in the study’s focus on evaluating the alignment of programs with institutional objectives and tracking their effectiveness.

Nabulu (2015) highlights evaluations as essential for measuring effectiveness, guiding future projects, and ensuring equitable benefit distribution. This aligns with the study’s findings, where evaluations assess outcomes such as academic performance and behavioral changes while informing future program improvements and ensuring equity among stakeholders.

The high ratings for the evaluation practices in this study reflect the recognition of the multifaceted roles evaluations play, as discussed by Ntsele (2014) and Nabulu (2015). Organizations are increasingly using evaluations not only to assess immediate impacts but also to inform long-term planning, attract support, and ensure that resources are distributed equitably across different groups.

Table 8

The Summary Table in the Level of Implementation of the Intervention Program of the Selected Elementary School in the Fourth Congressional District of Quezon

Component	Composite Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Strategic Planning and Management	4.34	0.651	PGtE
Budgeting	4.02	0.816	PGE
Implementation	4.22	0.713	PGtE
Monitoring	4.27	0.668	PGtE
Evaluation	4.28	0.702	PGtE
Grand Mean	4.23	0.710	PGtE

Legend:

Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Practiced to the Greatest Extent (PGtE)
3.40 – 4.19	Practiced to the Great Extent (PGE)
2.60 – 3.39	Practiced to the Moderate Extent (PME)
1.80 – 2.59	Practiced to the Less Extent (PLE)
1.00 – 1.79	Did Not Practice at All (DNP)

The data presented in Table 8 reveals a comprehensive summary of the implementation level of intervention programs within selected elementary schools in the 4th Congressional District of Quezon. Analyzing each component individually reveals significant insights into the effectiveness of these programs.

Strategic planning emerges as a standout area, with a composite mean (M) of 4.34 (SD = 0.651), indicating it is practiced to the greatest extent (PGtE). This suggests that schools within the districts have robust strategic planning processes in place to guide their intervention programs. The relatively low standard deviation of 0.651 further underscores the high consensus among respondents regarding strategic planning practices.

While budgeting, with a composite mean of (M) 4.02 (SD = 0.816), is slightly low compared to Strategic planning, it still falls within the category of “Practiced to the Great Extent (PGE). However, the higher standard deviation of (SD = 0.816) suggests some variability in responses regarding budgeting practices. Implementation, monitoring, and evaluation all exhibit strong performance, with composite means of (M) 4.22, 4.27, and 4.28, respectively, all falling within the category of being “Practiced to the Greatest Extent” (PGtE). This indicates that implementation, monitoring, and evaluation practices within intervention programs are highly implemented and valued by the respondents. The relatively low standard deviations across these components suggest a high level of agreement among respondents regarding the effectiveness of these practices.

Overall, the grand mean (M) of 4.23, also falling within the PGtE category, represents the collective level of implementation across all components. This indicates a high implementation of intervention programs within the district's elementary schools. The consistent ratings across various components reflect a well-rounded and comprehensive approach to intervention program implementation.

Supporting this study, insights from Kadlong & Parcon (2016), and Arenque (2021) shed light on various dimensions of SBM implementation within educational contexts, emphasizing the importance of stakeholder engagement, leadership dynamics, and effective governance structures in driving educational reforms. On the other hand, UNESCO Global Education Monitoring Report (2019): Stresses the importance of school funding mechanisms, like MOOE, in maintaining infrastructure, purchasing educational resources, and enhancing overall learning outcomes.

Part III. Significant Difference in the Level of Management Practices When Grouped According to School Profile

Table 9

Statistical Table Showing the Significant Difference in the Level of Management Practices When Grouped According to School Profile

Test Variable	Grouping Variables	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Level of Implementation	Designation of School Heads	.073	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Educational Attainment of School Heads	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	School Size Category	.070	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho

Statistical Table 9 presents the significant difference in the level of management practices when grouped according to school profile variables. The level of implementation for each grouping variable varies and is assessed through p-values, which help determine the significance of the observed differences. When considering the designation of school heads as the grouping variable, the Obtained p-value of .073 suggests no significant difference in the level of Implementation based on this criterion. Therefore, the

interpretation suggests that the results are not statistically significant, leading to the decision not to reject the null hypothesis (Do Not Reject Ho).

Conversely, when examining the educational attainment of school heads, the p-value is calculated as .000, indicating a statistically significant difference in the level of implementation based on this variable. Consequently, the interpretation suggests significance (Significant), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (Reject Ho).

Regarding the school category as the grouping variable, the obtained p-value of .070 indicates no significant difference in the level of implementation among different school categories. Thus, the interpretation suggests that the results are not statistically significant, leading to the decision not to reject the null hypothesis (Do Not Reject Ho).

In essence, the analysis reveals significant variations in management practices, primarily influenced by the educational backgrounds of school leaders. Notably, no significant differences were observed based on the designation of school heads. This underscores the critical role of educational attainment in shaping the effectiveness of management practices within the schools analyzed.

In association with the findings of this study, Kaditong et al. (2016) emphasizes the importance of educational attainment for effective leadership in SBM, which directly supports the finding that educational background significantly affects the implementation of intervention programs in schools. Moreover, Arenque (2021) highlights the role of stakeholder engagement in SBM success, which is indirectly supported by the finding that school heads with higher educational attainment likely excel at engaging stakeholders and ensuring better implementation of management practices.

Part IV. Institutional Performance of the School’s Respondents Based on the School-Based Management (SBM) Level of Practice

Table 10 *The Institutional Performance of the School’s Respondents Based on the SBM Level*

School	SBMPI Result	SBMAS(DOD) Result	Total	SBM Level of Practice
A	0.83	1.15	1.98	Level II Maturing
B	0.95	1.15	2.10	Level II Maturing
C	0.69	0.96	1.65	Level II Maturing
D	0.99	1.20	2.19	Level II Maturing
E	1.16	1.15	2.31	Level II Maturing
F	0.84	0.87	1.71	Level II Maturing
G	0.63	0.79	1.42	Level II Maturing
H	0.51	0.97	1.48	Level II Maturing
I	0.58	0.66	1.24	Level I Developing
J	0.51	1.15	1.66	Level II Maturing
K	0.15	.63	0.78	Level I Developing
	0.71	0.97	1.68	Level II Maturing
SBM Level		Frequency	Percentage	
Level 1		2	18.18	
Level 2		9	81.82	
Total		11	100.00	

The analysis of schools' institutional performance based on their SBM levels, as outlined in Table 10, reveals a spectrum of progress in SBM implementation across the schools. Most schools (81.82%) fall within Level II (Maturing), indicating that these institutions have made substantial strides in the adoption and execution of SBM practices. These schools show a positive trajectory toward effective governance and operational practices, aligning with the principles of decentralization highlighted by Murphy (1991). His work underscores how empowering schools with decision-making authority fosters ownership and responsibility, leading to enhanced organizational effectiveness. The majority of schools at Level II have likely implemented strategies that reflect greater stakeholder involvement, which resonates with Murphy's view of decentralization as a driver of organizational success.

In contrast, two schools (I and K), which are still in Level I (Developing), present an opportunity for targeted intervention. The findings suggest that these schools require focused support to strengthen their SBM frameworks. This need for intervention is consistent with Dewey's (1916) advocacy for teacher input and participatory governance, as schools at this foundational level may still be grappling with fully integrating stakeholder engagement and decision-making processes.

Furthermore, Gamage's (1996) theoretical framework aligns with the findings by framing SBM as an evolution toward democratic governance structures. Schools in Level II are more likely to benefit from these decentralized practices, fostering innovation, accountability, and adaptability. As these schools continue to mature in their SBM implementation, the shift toward increased stakeholder engagement and decentralized decision-making is likely to promote a culture of continuous improvement. This, in turn, supports Gamage's perspective that SBM is a key strategy for promoting accountability and fostering positive institutional change.

The varying levels of SBM implementation highlight the need for schools at Level I to be supported in their development of SBM level practice, while those at Level II can share best practices and foster a collaborative environment. By emphasizing decentralization and participatory governance, as proposed by Murphy (1991) and Gamage (1996), the study's findings suggest that targeted support and collaboration can lead to sustained growth and improvement across all schools.

Part V. Significant Relationship Between the Level of Management Practices of Intervention Programs and School’s Institutional Performance Through SBM Level of Practice

Table 11

Statistical Table Showing the Significant Relationship Between the Level of Implementation of Intervention Programs in Selected Elementary Schools and the School’s Performance

Correlations		Performance	Level of implementation	Interpretation	Decision
Performance	Correlation (r)	1.000	.324**		
	p-value	.	.000		
Spearman's rho	N	162	162	Significant	Reject Ho
	Correlation (r)	.324**	1.000		
Level of implementation	p-value	.000	.		
	n	162	162		

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

Table 11 presents the statistical relationship between the levels of implementation of intervention programs in selected elementary schools and their performance, as measured By Spearman's rho correlation coefficient.

The correlation coefficient between performance and the level of implementation was calculated at 0.324**, indicating a moderate positive correlation between these variables. This suggests that as the level of implementation of intervention programs increases, there tends to be a corresponding moderate improvement in school performance. The correlation is deemed statistically significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), denoted by **.

The p-value associated with the correlation coefficient is calculated as .000, indicating that the observed correlation is unlikely to have occurred by chance. With a p-value below the Typical significance threshold of 0.05, the result further supports, rejecting the null Hypothesis (Ho), reinforcing the significance of the observed correlation.

The statistical findings underscore a significant moderate correlation between the implementation of intervention programs and school performance, suggesting a moderate relationship between the two variables. Schools exhibiting higher levels of implementation tend to yield improve performance outcomes that contribute to SBM principles criterion indicator level 3, particularly to Curriculum and Instruction, a trend that prompts rejecting the null hypothesis. This observation emphasizes the pivotal role of intervention program

implementation in shaping positive academic outcomes across elementary public schools in Quezon's fourth congressional district division.

This finding is supported by, Hawthorne (2023) which delves into the intricacies of educational interventions, defining them as strategic deviations from standard instructional practices tailored to address specific learning needs and play a crucial role in enhancing academic performance. More robust and cohesive interventions, particularly those that address specific learning challenges, tend to lead to better academic outcomes.

Additionally, Tolentino (2023) further reinforces the importance of teacher involvement and parental engagement in the success of reading intervention programs. By conceptualizing intervention programs as collections of interrelated projects, Brewitt, (2019) highlights the importance of coordination and collaboration to achieve overarching educational goals.

Part VI. Proposed Action Plan

Considering the result of the recent research study assessing the level of management practices in the implementation of intervention programs in selected public elementary school in the fourth congressional district division of Quezon it's evident that strategic planning and management, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation have been widely adopted which determined as highly implemented and practiced to the greatest extent in management practices. Notably, budgeting emerged as a significant area of concern, as practiced to the great extent only which is identified as the lowest among the other management practices, reflecting a substantial commitment to financial planning and resource allocation. Building upon this foundation, the proposed action plan aims to further enhance budgeting practices to optimize resource utilization and ensure the sustained success of intervention program. Through strategic interventions and targeted improvements, seeking to elevate budgeting practices to even greater and greatest heights, aligning financial strategies with overarching organizational objectives and fostering a culture of fiscal responsibility and efficiency. The innovative feature of the plan that the researcher contribute is the use of the following:

1. Digital Budgeting Tools using software like Google Sheets to track and allocate funds, implement online dashboards to provide real-time updates and transparency for stakeholders.
2. Data-Driven Decision-Making to leverage data analytics to prioritize budget allocation based on the program's historical performance and projected impact. Use forecasting models to estimate costs and benefits of each intervention.
3. Participatory Budgeting to engage stakeholders, including teachers, parents, and students, in the budgeting process through workshops and online surveys, and collect diverse input to ensure the budget aligns with the program's priorities and community needs.

4. Resource Optimization to incorporate cost-effective strategies, such as utilizing open educational resources (OERs) or collaborating with other organizations for shared resources.

Adopt a zero-based budgeting approach to justify each expense in alignment with program goals.

5. Performance-Based Allocation - tie budget allocation to measurable outcomes to ensure funds are used effectively and regularly review and adjust the budget based on performance metrics and program milestones.

6. Green Budgeting Practices-Incorporate sustainable practices, such as minimizing paper use or energy-efficient project implementation, to reduce costs and environmental impact.

7. Transparent Reporting- Develop user-friendly financial reports and visuals to share progress with stakeholders. Use blockchain for secure and transparent tracking of funds.

DISCUSSION

This part outlines the key findings of the study, highlighting the most significant results.

1. Profile of the School

1.1. Majority of respondents hold the position of Principal, constituting 63.64% (7) of the total, followed by Head Teachers at 27.27% (3), and Teachers in Charge at 9.09% (1)

1.2 In terms of education, most of the school heads are master's degree holders, comprising 36.36% (4), while 27.27% (3) have earned units toward a doctorate. Additionally, 18.18% (2) have earned units in a master's program, and 18.18% (2) hold a doctoral degree. It is important to note that no respondent holds only a bachelor's degree.

1.3. Out of 11 schools under the scope of the study. (4) 36.36% are small, 4 (36.36%) are large and the remaining (3) 27.27% are categorized as medium.

2. Level of Management Practices of the Respondents in the Implementation of Intervention Programs:

2.1. Strategic Planning and Management

The level of strategic planning and management practices related to the execution of intervention programs among respondents is measured on a five-point scale, with one indicating low practice and five indicating substantial practice. Generally, with a composite mean score of 4.34 and a standard deviation of 0.651, which indicates that

practices are primarily practiced to the greatest extent, the Respondents show a high level of management practices in strategic planning and Intervention program implementation.

2.2. Budgeting

Overall, the management practices related to budgeting for intervention programs are rated relatively high, with a composite mean of 4.02. This indicates that, on average, these practices are perceived to be implemented to a great extent; however, it classifies last among the five levels of management practices evaluated.

2.3. Implementation

The respondents' level of management practices in implementing intervention programs shows that most indicators have mean scores higher than 4.00, indicating that respondents believe these management practices are being used to a greater or greatest extent, with a composite mean of 4.22. This shows that the mechanisms used by schools to execute Intervention programs are generally effective.

2.4. Monitoring

The respondents believe that the level of management practices related to monitoring intervention programs is either fully adopted or primarily implemented, with a composite mean of 4.27. This score indicates a strong commitment to efficient monitoring procedures within the examined organizations.

2.5. Evaluation

With mean scores ranging from 4.22 to 4.33 and a composite mean of 4.28, the level of management practices employed by the respondents in implementing intervention programs in terms of evaluation is described as practiced to the greatest extent. This suggests that respondents generally perceive management practices related to the evaluation of intervention programs as highly implemented, indicating a strong commitment to conducting efficient evaluations.

3. There are significant differences in management practices based on the academic degrees held by school heads. However, no significant differences were found concerning the designation of school heads or the size category of the schools. In the context of the schools under analysis, this emphasizes how crucial educational attainment influences management practices.
4. There is a favorable trend towards the effective implementation of school-based management (SBM) practices, as evidenced by the majority of the nine (9) selected public elementary schools, mainly under the supervision of the school principal, specifically with the school size falls under the small, medium, and large categories, being in the Level II Maturing stage. To improve their institutional performance and the implementation of School-Based Management (SBM), two schools categorized as small and managed by teachers-in-charge, located in remote areas, stand out as needing more targeted attention and assistance. The current analysis highlights the variation in performance levels among educational institutions. It underscores the

importance of targeted interventions and support systems to enhance the implementation of School-Based Management (SBM) and improve overall institutional performance.

5. The statistical results show a significant correlation between school performance through SBM level of practice and the implementation of intervention programs. In particular, schools with higher implementation levels typically demonstrate better performance outcomes. Based on the Statistical analysis and significance level, the null hypothesis is thus rejected, suggesting a significant correlation between the degree of intervention program implementation and school performance in the selected public elementary schools in Quezon's Fourth Congressional District.
6. An action plan was developed to equip schools with effective management practices for implementing intervention programs. This plan aims not only to enhance these practices but also to improve overall institutional performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings as summarized, the following statement are concluded:

1. The respondent school profile reflects essential trends within educational leadership. Principals, as the predominant respondents, underscore their pivotal role as decision-makers in the field. The educational attainment of school heads highlights a strong commitment to advanced education. The majority of respondents are affiliated with large schools, followed by small schools, with medium schools coming last. Educational leadership roles are more prevalent in larger institutions, highlighting the scale and diversity of the schools under their supervision and the varying demands associated with each school size.
2. The level of management practices among respondents regarding the implementation of intervention programs—particularly in terms of strategic planning and management, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation—are evidently practiced and predominantly executed to a great extent, reflecting a solid commitment to optimizing educational interventions. However, some areas in budgeting, such as resource allocation and community engagement, show slightly lower scores. Overall, the findings suggest a proactive and comprehensive approach to managing intervention programs. These practices are crucial for ensuring the effectiveness, sustainability, and positive impact of educational interventions on student outcomes and institutional performance.
3. The level of implementation of intervention programs by school heads, when grouped according to school profile, shows that the designation of school heads is not statistically significant; thus, the hypothesis is accepted. The educational attainment of school heads is statistically different; therefore, the hypothesis is rejected. Regarding school category, the results indicate no significant difference in the level of implementation among different school categories; thus, the hypothesis is accepted.

4. The institutional performance of schools based on School-Based Management (SBM) level of practice shows encouraging results, with most schools achieving Level 2. This indicates a solid foundation in institutional management and effective implementation of SBM practices. However, the presence of some schools at Level 1 highlights areas where growth and development are possible, suggesting a need for focused support and training. Encouraging collaboration between Level 2 and Level 1 schools through the sharing of best practices could foster a supportive environment that promotes overall improvement in management practices across institutions.

5. There is a significant relationship between the implementation of intervention programs and school performance through SBM level of practice; therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

6. An action plan was developed based on the results to ensure the effective implementation of the intervention programs.

Recommendations

Given the gathered data, following a thorough evaluation and conclusions, the following recommendations were offered:

1. The profile of the respondents—specifically regarding the designation of the school head, educational attainment, and school category—discloses several notable trends in the management practices related to the implementation of intervention programs, which also have a significant relationship with institutional performance. Thus, the institutions may revisit and may give necessary support in terms of the following:

Professional Development Programs: Provide principal-specific professional development opportunities to help them stay current with emerging trends in Education and strengthen their leadership abilities.

Advanced Degree Incentives: Offer incentives or scholarships to those who wish to pursue master's or doctoral degrees in order to encourage future educational leaders to continue their education.

Research and Analysis: Conduct further research and analysis to investigate the reasons behind the preference for larger educational institutions and the prevalence of principals with advanced degrees.

Networking Opportunities: Encourage educational leaders, particularly those from larger institutions, to network and share ideas, tactics, and best practices.

Policy Implications: Consider the policy implications for educational leadership requirements and explore the establishment of minimum criteria or standards for educational leadership positions.

2. The respondents' level of management practices regarding the implementation of the intervention programs in terms of strategic planning and management, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation revealed that the implementation of intervention programs is described as "practiced to the greatest extent." While in budgeting, it was described as "practiced to the Great Extent." However, there are some respondents who answer fall into the "practiced to the Less Extent" and "did not practice at all." Thus, there is a need for improvement in the management practice in terms of budgeting. The following recommendations are suggested:

Enhanced Reporting Practices: Improving reporting practices, particularly regarding budget status and its impact on program outcomes, can provide greater transparency and accountability. Transparent and regular reporting can help stakeholders, make informed decisions and optimize resource allocation.

Capacity Building: School organizations should invest in continuous training and development programs for staff involved in budget management. This investment will ensure that personnel possess the necessary skills and knowledge to manage budgets effectively, adapt to changing requirements, and maximize program outcomes.

Surplus Budget Management: Developing clear policies and procedures for managing surplus budget funds can help ensure responsible and strategic reinvestment. Organizations should establish guidelines for reallocating surplus funds to areas that align with program goals and priorities.

3. Given the significant impact of educational attainment on management practices among school heads, it is recommended that educational institutions prioritize hiring and promoting individuals with higher levels of education for Leadership positions. Investing in the professional development and academic qualifications of school leaders can improve management practices, ultimately enhancing the overall functioning and performance of schools.

4. Based on research data findings and conclusions of institutional performance of the school's respondents based on the SBM level of practice, here are some of the recommendations:

Tailored Support Programs: Develop customized support programs for Schools I and K to address their needs and challenges in implementing School-Based Management (SBM) level of practice.

Peer Learning Networks: Facilitate peer learning networks among schools to Share best practices and lessons learned, fostering collaboration and mutual support in advancing SBM implementation.

Capacity Building Workshops: Implement workshops aimed at enhancing capacity in School-Based Management (SBM) principles, leadership skills, and effective governance structures for school administrators, teachers, and staff across all schools.

Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation: Implement a robust monitoring and evaluation system to track progress, identify areas for improvement, and ensure accountability in SBM implementation across all schools.

Resource Allocation Review: Review resource allocation mechanisms to ensure equitable distribution of resources and support services, mainly to schools needing additional assistance like Schools I and K.

Stakeholder Engagement: Foster greater stakeholder engagement, involving parents, community members, and local authorities to garner support and involvement in advancing SBM level of practice and improving institutional performance.

Long-Term Sustainability Plans: Develop long-term sustainability plans for SBM implementation, including strategies for ongoing training, support, and capacity development to maintain momentum and drive continuous improvement in all Schools.

5.The proposed action plan developed by the researcher as an output of this study may be presented to the Department of Education Division of Quezon for evaluation and possible implementation.

6.Future researchers may conduct study that will determine the other factors that will contribute to the attainment of higher SBM level of practice.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study ensured the informed consent was given to the following respondents. Freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interests exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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